

Creating robotics paths in seconds

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Abstract: The RoProMan project, led by Furtwangen University and CleanControlling GmbH, developed a user-friendly robotic programming system for particle extraction on 3D objects by suction. The innovation: programmable without prior knowledge. Application: technical cleanliness, especially analysis of particulate contamination, e.g. on electronic components, to prevent irreversible damage. Previously carried out manually, this causes significant differences in the analysis results due to variable movement parameters. Result: Three basic concepts, the most promising of which is a model-based approach based on a 3D model. Motion sequences are calculated offline via Matlab and transferred to the robot controller, which enables consistent extraction. Finally, the concept was successfully tested in application-oriented feasibility studies.

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I. Introduction

In the RoProMan project, Furtwangen University (HFU) worked together with CleanControlling GmbH to develop a concept for the intuitive programming of robots for the extraction of particles on three-dimensional objects by means of extraction. The programming should be so "simple" that it can be carried out without programming knowledge. The application of the method is in the field of technical cleanliness, in particular in the analysis of particulate surface impurities that are found on technical components, which can cause irreversible damage, e.g. due to short circuits, on electronic components. In order to be able to analyze these particulate impurities, they must be extracted from the surface as reproducibly as possible, i.e. detached before they can be sent for analysis.

II. Starting point

The extraction process described above has so far been carried out exclusively manually. As a result, differences in movement parameters, such as speed or trajectory movement of the suction nozzle, arise, especially during repeated extraction processes. This results in significant differences in the analysis results, which are to be significantly improved by the robot-guided application and the very comparable movement parameters.

III. Solution

A 3-dimensional test specimen is to be captured by a subsystem and translated into a three-dimensional model so that it can be translated by a software application into a code readable by the handling system. If the model of the test specimen is already available, it is optionally possible to enter the handling system's movement instructions directly during conversion. For this purpose, the calculated orbital movement is specified as points in the robot coordinate system, which are then converted into axis coordinates and executed by the axes. The application therefore requires the calculation of the Cartesian coordinates of the trajectory relative to the current component. The trajectory is calculated offline using a Matlab application and then transferred to the controller.

The concrete implementation generates an STL envelope model from existing CAD data. From this, a two-dimensional map of the surface is generated over several steps. The surface of the board is then available as a binary $n \times m$ matrix. Where n and m stand for the resolution. Points where there is no obstacle have the entry 0, points within an obstacle have the entry 1. The obstacles are represented as polygons. Then, so-called events are assigned to all vertices of each polygon. An event is a kind of signpost for the algorithm with various properties. Depending on the position of the individual events, the surface of the board can be broken down into partial surfaces (hereinafter referred to as cells), each of which is free of obstacles. The following Figure 1 shows four cells, which together describe the entire open space of an example geometry.

Figure 1: Dividing an example surface with an obstacle into four cells. The Critical Point shown corresponds to an event. Source: [1]

A ZigZag pattern is used to generate the area-filling path within the cells. The so-called Boustrophedon algorithm [2] is used for this purpose. When calculating the pattern, all parameters are calculated from the diameter of the suction nozzle to avoid collision of the suction nozzle with the edges of the cell. The reason for this is that there can be obstacles at the edges of the cells. In addition, overlapping

of the lanes can be minimized. Depending on the geometry, however, very small or narrow cells can be formed after disassembly. Depending on the position of these, it cannot be guaranteed that the suction nozzle would fit through them. For this reason, the cells are checked for a parameterizable minimum size before calculating the ZigZag path. The following Figure 2 shows the completed tracks on an exemplary component and their real implementation.

Figure 2: Transfer to the real system

III. Results and discussion

Based on the detailed catalogue of requirements, 3 basic concepts for the solution could be developed. The most promising solution was seen in a model-based approach based on a digital three-dimensional model of the component to be extracted. This model is either available in the form of CAD data or must be generated in advance on the basis of a real representative using a 3D scanner. Based on this, the motion sequence for the application-specific and optimal movement of the extraction is calculated offline using an algorithm developed for this purpose. This is based on a Matlab application, which divides the existing 3D model into many different planes and creates the required motion sequence based on 6 degrees of freedom (trajectory) fully automatically.

This sequence of movements is transferred to the robot's control system so that it travels along the calculated path. The model-based approach has been elaborated so far.

Figure 3: Concept of the process and the sub-functions of the project

IV. Conclusions

The RoProMan project, a collaboration between Furtwangen University and CleanControlling GmbH, successfully developed an intuitive robotic programming system for particle extraction on 3D objects. This innovation, which requires no prior programming knowledge, significantly improves the consistency and accuracy of particulate contamination analysis on technical components. The project introduced a model-based approach using 3D models and offline calculations via Matlab to generate precise motion sequences for the robot. This method was validated through application-oriented feasibility studies, demonstrating its potential to enhance technical cleanliness and prevent damage to electronic components. The project's outcomes highlight the importance of user-friendly robotic solutions in maintaining high standards of technical cleanliness.

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